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Research Article

**MANAGING THE ACUTE MICROBIAL RHINOSINUSITIS
AND USE OF LEVOFLOXACIN & AMOXICILLIN
CLAVULANATE: A COMPARATIVE RESEARCH**

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¹House Officer, Mayo Hospital Lahore**Abstract**

Objective: In treating the acute microbial rhinosinusitis the Comparison for the efficiency among Levofloxacin and Amoxicillin Clavulanate was the objective of the study.

Materials & Methods: We used the Department of Otorhinolaryngology at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for the present comparison research from January to August 2017. Three hundred and sixty (360) patients of acute microbial sinusitis participated in the research.

Results: In this current research we compared the Mean ages were Group A (35.73 ± 7.31) and Group B (35.91 ± 8.24). In population ($N=360$) the percentage of Males was 39.72% with 143 participants and percentage of Females was 60.28% with 217 participants. Efficacy was present among 172 participants with 95.56% in Group B (Levofloxacin) and 146 participants with 81.11% Group A (Amoxicillin-clavulanate) having p-value (0.00).

Conclusion: We found out that for managing the acute microbial rhinosinusitis (sign & symptoms relief) levofloxacin is more efficient and cost-effective as compared to amoxicillin-clavulanate.

Keywords: Rhinosinusitis, Microbial, Amoxicillin, Levofloxacin

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INTRODUCTION:

Severe Rhinosinusitis or (ARS) is a severe virus related or microbial infection, which cause swelling and tenderness of paranasal sinuses and mucosa of the nose [1]. A viral cause is common in severe Rhinosinusitis (ARS) cases, but the microbial cause is also very common. Majority of the sufferers of severe Rhinosinusitis (ARS) improve without using antibiotics but this treatment would be sought for patients with extended and alarming signs. Whether Rhinosinusitis (ARS) having source virus related or not related to virus source, if it is presently less than twelve weeks is acute, when times go past this duration it is chronic, when more than three occurrences in 1 year it is recurrent acute. Signs related to Rhinosinusitis (ARS) disappear without cure in patients (40%). But therapeutic treatment is necessary for relieving the severe symptoms and to cater to unforeseen circumstances which may lead it to chronic stage [2]. To reduce harshness, to reduce the length of disorder, to remove the infection, and to stop severe difficulties are the mandatory features of managing the acute sinusitis. Its patients get treatment in ordinary clinics. Patients get additional treatment on some following occasions:

- i. Continuous decline even in suitable use of antibiotics
- ii. Recurring sinusitis
- iii. Signs keep on after two sessions with the treatment of antibiotics
- iv. Comorbidity occur with a deficiency in the immune system, nosocomial infection, or the presence of sinusitis related problems

In managing the Acute Sinusitis providing the suitable effluence, moreover suitable treatment of microbial causes [3]. A team over Practice Parameters used for Allergy & Immunology recommends that after three to five days therapy we should measure the symptoms and carry the therapy if we see any betterment. The combination of intranasal corticosteroid and antibiotic diminishes the signs as compared to the use of just antibiotic [3]. We can make effluence of sinus surgically as well as medically. Belligerent treatment of patients of Acute Sinusitis in ICU to evade infection, e.g., for affluence, the removal of nasogastric and nasotracheal tubes either through medicine or through surgery [4]. Pynnonen et al did a research in an academic set-up and recommends the heavy use of antibiotic in mild acute sinusitis. Around 66 % use antibiotics, its use depends on giving a person, his expertise (increased use of antibiotics in an emergency) and presence of medicinal apprentice [4]. In both situations' laboratory-oriented studies and in field studies,

topical nasal corticosteroids as well as anti-microbial drugs whether we use these separately or combinedly has great effects [5 – 7]. Cefadroxil or Amoxicillin-clavulanate has great effects in case of mild acute Rhinosinusitis but having any previous history of antibiotic usage. Whereas Moxifloxacin or Levofloxacin are effective in moderate Rhinosinusitis having a history of antibiotic usage. Cephalosporins (ceftriaxone, cefixime cefotaxime) are effective in severe cases [8 – 10]. High efficacy is present in amoxicillin-clavulanate upon levofloxacin (Europe) [11 – 12]. But this situation is not likely in Pakistan and no such records are present. Comparison of medical efficacy of two (2) most widely taken medicines for the cure of Rhinosinusitis in Pakistan was the rationale of the present research. For treating microbial Rhinosinusitis, Levofloxacin is cost-effective than amoxicillin-clavulanate in current research.

Operational Definitions:

Acute Microbial Rhinosinusitis: We considered undermentioned constraints for the purpose of diagnosis:

- a. Recorded the signs like release from nose, the sensation of obstruction in the nose, pain in the head, poor sense of smell (cacostmia) in hours/day and frequency/day.
- b. ENT doctor examines the reports like post nasal drip, mucopurulent nasal release in meatus, and swollen and reddish nasal turbinate.

For acute microbial rhinosinusitis diagnosis, 04 or more symptoms and 02 or more signs are necessary for more than ten days or deteriorating symptoms seven days later. We measured the efficacy on the 11th day by undermentioned constraint i.e., full recovery from symptoms & signs.

Amoxicillin-Clavulanate: A modest range, bacteriolytic, β lactam antibiotic for treating microbial contagions owing to vulnerable micro-organisms. We gave this one gram twelve hourly over ten days in this research (Group A).

Levofloxacin: A chemotherapeutic anti-infection of the fluoroquinolone category utilized for treating serious microbial diseases or microbial contaminations that are not treatable by other antibiotic categories. We utilized it in a portion of 250 mg twelve hourly over ten days in this research (Group B).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We used the Department of Otorhinolaryngology at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for the present comparison

research from January to August 2017. Three hundred and sixty (360) patients of acute microbial sinusitis participated in the research. We take the Patients (N=360) who are meeting the criteria of acute microbial sinusitis with age range 15 – 55 years from both genders. We did not include some patients e.g., using another anti-biotic, less period and not on given dose, any disease like Pneumonia etc., antipathy with Amoxicillin-clavulanate or Levofloxacin, diabetic patients, patients having a history of sinus nasal surgery, pregnant women and feeding mothers. We randomly divided the patients into 2 equivalent groups (A & B). We gave nasal spray (xylometazoline) with nasal decongestant as well as steam inhalation in the same amount and time. Amoxicillin-clavulanate Group (A) obtained 1 gram twelve hourly over ten days and Levofloxacin Group (B) obtained 250 milligrams twelve hourly over ten days. We observed the subjects closely and monitored any side effect. We pursued the subjects on phone calls. We evaluated the subjects for any indication that is alarming. We documented

indication on very first and on 11th appointment after ending treatment. We used a form to obtain data, which later ran through SPSS. We present the Arithmetical data in Mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) and categorical data in frequency (f) and percentage (%). We used Chi-square method to compare the data of two groups. Value of p was significant at 0.05.

RESULTS:

Age bracket was 15 to 55 years having Average (mean) age (35.79 ± 7.86), (Group A = 35.73 ± 7.31) and (Group B = 35.91 ± 8.24) years. Average (mean) of symptoms was (4.19 ± 2.36) weeks. Length of disease was (4.33 ± 2.72) and (4.28 ± 2.60) weeks for Group (A) and Group (B) respectively. We compared the efficacy among the two groups. Treatment effectiveness in the group (A) 146 patients with a percentage of 81.11 and in the group (B) it was 172 patients with a percentage of 95.56. There is significant efficacy difference in two groups with p-value = 0.00 as depicted in Table – I.

Table – I: Group Wise Positive and Negative Efficacy

Groups		Positive Efficacy	Negative Efficacy	P-Value
Group – A	Number	146	34	0.00
	Percentage	81.11	18.89	
Group – B	Number	172	9	
	Percentage	95.56	4.44	

We divided the subjects into three groups (15 – 30) years, (31 – 45) years and (46 – 55) years. Treatment effectiveness in Group (B) was 98.04% with 50 patients, in Group (A) it was 86.79% with 46 patients. The efficacy variance among the two group was significant with $p = 0.031$. Efficacy of treatment in age group (31 – 45) was 92.42% in sixty-one (61) patients of Group (B) and 74.60% in forty-seven (47) patients of Group (A). The variance of efficacy in these two groups was significant at 0.006. Efficacy of treatment in age group (46 – 55) was 96.83% in sixty-one (61) of Group (B) and 82.81% in fifty-three (53) patients of Group (A). The variance of efficacy in these two groups was significant at 0.009 as depicted in Table – II.

Table – II: Group Wise Age Stratification

Age (Years)		Group - A		Group - B		P-Value
		Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	
15 to 30	Number	46	7	50	1	0.031
	Percentage	86.79	13.21	98.04	1.96	
31 to 45	Number	47	16	61	5	0.006
	Percentage	74.60	25.40	92.42	7.58	
46 to 55	Number	53	11	2	61	0.009
	Percentage	82.81	17.19	96.83	3.17	

In ≤ 4 weeks of illness, treatment efficacy was 98.17% in 107 patients of the group (B) and 87.74% in ninety-three (93) patients of the group (A). The variance of efficacy in these two groups was significant at 0.003. In > 4 weeks of disorder, treatment effectiveness was 91.55% in sixty-five (65) patients of the group (B) and 71.62% in fifty-three (53) patients of Group (A), the variance between groups was significant at $p = 0.002$ as depicted in Table – III.

Table – III: Group Wise Disease Duration Stratification

Disease Duration (Weeks)		Group - A		Group - B		P-Value
		Yes	No	Yes	No	
$\leq$ Four	Number	107	2	93	13	0.003
	Percentage	98.17	1.83	87.74	12.26	
$>$ Four	Number	65	6	53	21	0.002
	Percentage	91.55	8.45	71.62	28.39	

In group (B) treatment effectiveness was present in seventy (70) male patients with 95.89% and in the group (A) fifty-five (55) with 78.57% and its variance is significant at $p = 0.002$. In group (B) treatment effectiveness was present in 102 female patients with 95.33% and in the group (A) ninety-one (91) female patients with 82.73% and its variance is significant at $p = 0.003$ as depicted in Table – IV.

Table – IV: Gender Distribution among Groups

Gender		Group – A		Group – B		P-Value
		Yes	No	Yes	No	
Male	Number	70	3	55	15	0.002
	Percentage	95.89	4.11	78.57	21.43	
Female	Number	102	5	91	19	0.003
	Percentage	95.33	4.67	82.73	17.27	

DISCUSSION:

There are not any Random Controlled Trials (RCT) of the anti-biotic method of managing ABRS by sinus articulate trends ahead and afterwards of treatment but some non-random methods microbiological treatments. Five (5) Random Controlled Trials (RCT) and two (2) meta-analysis compared anti-biotics normally Amoxicillin And Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (TMP - SMX; Bactrim, Septra) used in a pair of placebo (control). Its results showed medical effectiveness as per patient's requirement [13]. We treated 47% patients by using antibiotics and 32% of patients get healthy in the control group over ten to fourteen days. We gave treatment to 81% of patients by using anti-biotics and 66% in control get the treatment, one out of seven patient shows improvement in health by anti-biotics. Due to the lack of precise diagnosis, the effectiveness of treatment is miscalculated [13]. We examined Macrolides (azithromycin [Zithromax] and clarithromycin [Biaxin]), Cephalosporins (cefuroxime [Ceftin] & cefixime [Suprax]), Amoxicillin-clavulanate potassium (Augmentin) broadly [14]. These medicines get more than 80% achievement ratio. Fluoroquinolones is less common for managing acute microbial Rhinosinusitis. Resolution ratio of Ciprofloxacin (Cipro) and cefuroxime is 90% in primary care set-up [15]. In open-label RCT clarithromycin had ninety-three percent (93%) success ratio and levofloxacin (Levaquin) had ninety-six percent (96%) ninety-three percent (93%) success ratio [16]. Efficacy was present among 172 participants with 95.56% in Group B (Levofloxacin) and 146 participants with 81.11% Group A (Amoxicillin-clavulanate) having p value (0.00) [17]. In this research for managing Maxillary Sinusitis, we related the medical efficacy and microbiological reaction of two medicines co-amoxiclav & levofloxacin. In a random way, sixty (60) subjects orally obtained levofloxacin 300 Milligrams for one time in a day or co-amoxiclav 625 Milligrams thrice in the day over fourteen (14) days. We saw that radiological betterment was around 61.8% in case of levofloxacin in which 41.2% was resolution and 20.6% was betterment. In the case of co-amoxiclav, it was 61.5% in which 26.9% was resolution rate and 34.6% was betterment. Pre-treatment Maxillary Antral Aspiration cultures were +ve among twenty-eight (28) patients (82.4%) in a group of levofloxacin and twenty (20) patients in the group of co-amoxiclav. Obliteration from bacteria was around 78.5% in the group of LEV and around 70% in the group of COA, and there is not much difference in it. In the case of a group of LEV removal ratio regarding main pathogens of acute sinusitis was 66.7% for *P. aeruginosa* hundred percent for *S. pneumonia*, *S.*

aureus, *Neisseria* species and *H. influenzae*. In (1) experiment over-all 535 patients randomly obtained levofloxacin 500 Milligrams in a day or amoxicillin clavulanate (500 Milligrams of amoxicillin t.i.d. & 125 Milligrams of clavulanate t.i.d.) over ten to fourteen days [18].

Medical success ratio, two to five days after therapy, was 88.4% for patients who get treatment from levofloxacin, as compared to 87.3% for patients who get treatment from amoxicillin-clavulanate. In a similar research conducted by Adelglass et al contrasted amoxicillin-clavulanate and levofloxacin in Acute Bacterial Rhinosinusitis (ABRS) [19]. Success ratio (cured and improved) two to five days afterwards the conclusion of treatment was 88.4% for 267 observed patients obtaining levofloxacin and 87.3% for 268 observed patients obtaining amoxicillin-clavulanate. Our results indicated that one-time daily use of levofloxacin is beneficial and has good acceptance ratio as compared to thrice use of Amoxicillin-clavulanate in a day.

CONCLUSION:

Our research findings indicate that in terms of efficacy and cost-effectiveness levofloxacin is better as compared to Amoxicillin-clavulanate for managing the sign and symptoms of acute microbiological rhinosinusitis.

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